

Quinolino-6 :5- α -pyrones

By

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It has been shown (Dey and Goswami, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 531) that a class of heterocyclic substances containing the pyridine, benzene and pyrone rings fused to one another in the order named could be synthesised by the application of the Skraup reaction to aminocoumarins. These compounds were termed the ψ -1 : 8-isonapath-oxazones, but in view of the publication of a paper on the same subject under the title of "coumaro-quinolines" (Kondo and Tetsukichi Ui, *J. Pharm. S. c., Japan*, 1923, 498, 615), it is now proposed to redesignate these substances the quinolino- α -pyrones, a name which offers a better guide to the constitution of these substances than what was suggested before.

The different positions in these heterocyclic ring-systems may be conveniently numbered as follows :

Quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone

Quinolino-6:7- α -pyrone

7:8-Benzoquinolino-6:5- α -pyrone

5:6-Benzoquinolino-7:8- α -pyrone

7:8-Benzoquinolino-5:6- α -pyrone

In view of the interest attaching to these substances and the possibility of their exhibiting physiological activity, it seemed desirable to extend the series by studying methods of synthesis other than the Skraup process. An account is now given of the results of applying the Doebner-Miller reaction to 6-amino-coumarin, and to 6-amino-4-methyl- α -naphthapyrone. The former substance, reacting with paraldehyde, and with a mixture of paraldehyde and acetone, gave 2-methyl- and 2:4-dimethyl-quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone respectively, presumably in accordance with the following scheme :—

where X is H or CH₃.

The assumption that the amino-group reacts in the first

place with the hydroxy-group of the aldol molecule seems to afford the simplest explanation of the mechanism of this change and is also supported by the observation that in the parallel reaction between crotonic aldehyde and aniline, α -methyl-quinoline is almost exclusively formed.

The 2-methyl-quinolino-pyrone was obtained quite readily in a pure state, but in the preparation of the 2 : 4-dimethyl derivative the mixture of aldehyde and acetone had to be kept, saturated with hydrochloric acid, for about forty-eight hours before adding the amine hydrochloride: as on omitting this precaution considerable quantities of the monomethyl derivative were simultaneously formed and the separation of the mixture was found to be difficult and tedious.

These methyl derivatives do not differ materially in their general properties from the unsubstituted quinolino-pyrones described before. Their methiodides, however, are formed less readily and are also unstable, being partly decomposed into their constituents by boiling water. These methiodides have a pronounced yellow colour, but are colourless in aqueous solutions (*cf.* Day and Goswami, *loc. cit.*, 534).

Reduction of the methyl-quinolino-pyrones with tin and hydrochloric acid led to hydrogenation of the pyridine ring, but the process was slow and, in the case of the 2 : 4-dimethyl compound, the yield of the tetrahydro-derivative did not exceed 10 per cent. of the theoretical. This result is in agreement with the observation made by Braun, Gmelin and Schultheiss (*Ber.*, 1923, 56, 1338), *viz.*, that substitution of the pyridine ring by alkyl groups renders it more resistant to reduction. 2-Methyl-quinolino-6 : 5- α -pyrone forms a benzylidene derivative. This is colourless, but its hydrochloride and sulphate, which are sparingly soluble in water, have a bright yellow colour.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Methyl-quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone.

A mixture of 6-amino-coumarin (4 g.), fuming hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.), and paraldehyde (8 c.c.) was cooled in ice, saturated with hydrogen chloride and left overnight at the laboratory temperature in a loosely corked flask. The dark viscous product was heated at 130-135° for 3 hours, and the nearly dry mass was crushed and extracted with small quantities of boiling water until the solution was colourless. The extracts were cooled, and made alkaline with solid sodium bicarbonate, the yellow flocculent precipitate obtained in this way crystallised from 50 per cent. alcohol in pale yellow needles, m. p. 212-214° (yield 2-2.4 g.). The substance, on being twice crystallised from rectified spirit with the aid of animal charcoal, gave long colourless needles, m. p. 219-220°. (Found: C=73.8; H=4.3; N=6.3. $C_{13}H_9O_2N$ requires C=73.9; H=4.3; N=6.6 per cent.)

The substance is insoluble in cold water, very sparingly soluble in ether, benzene, petroleum, or cold 90 per cent. alcohol, moderately soluble in boiling water, and easily soluble in hot alcohol, chloroform and pyridine. When freshly precipitated, it dissolves in cold 10 per cent. caustic soda solution, but is insoluble in aqueous sodium carbonate or ammonia. 2-Methyl-quinolino-6:5- α -pyrone is soluble in hydrochloric, nitric or sulphuric acid (equal vols. of the concentrated acid and water), but from the clear solutions the respective salts

soon separate in colourless needles. (Found: Cl=14.6. $C_{13}H_9O_2N$, HCl requires Cl=14.3 per cent.)

The *mercurichloride* was obtained as a mass of soft colourless needles, and the *mercuri-iodide* as a pale yellow amorphous precipitate which slowly changed on standing to rhombic plates.

The *dichromate* crystallised from hot water in prismatic needles, deep yellow in colour. (Found: Cr_2O_3 =21.6. $(C_{13}H_9O_2N)_2$, $H_2Cr_2O_7$, $3\frac{1}{2}H_2O$ requires Cr_2O_3 =21.6 per cent.) The water of crystallisation in the dichromate could not be estimated as it was converted into a dark resinous mass at 100° .

The *picrate* crystallised from dilute alcohol in bright yellow needles. (Found: N=12.3. $C_{13}H_9O_2N$, $C_6H_3O_7N_3$ requires N=12.7 per cent.)

The *chloroplatinate* crystallised in yellow plates from hot water in which it dissolved very sparingly. (Found: Pt=23.5. $(C_{13}H_9O_2N)_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt=24.0 per cent.).

The *methiodide* was prepared by heating the base (1.5 g.), methyl iodide (1 c.c.) and methyl alcohol (5 c.c.) in a sealed tube at 100° for five hours. The product was extracted thrice with hot water, and the combined extracts were cooled, filtered from unchanged base, and evaporated in a vacuum over sulphuric acid, when golden yellow rectangular plates of the methiodide separated; m. p. $244-245^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: I=36.1. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2NI$ requires I=36.0 per cent.)

The methiodide dissolves readily in cold water, is insoluble in ether or benzene, and is decomposed by hot absolute alcohol.

The *benzylidene* derivative was prepared by heating the base (2 g.) with benzaldehyde (2 g.) at $150-160^\circ$ and

adding freshly fused zinc chloride (3 g.) from time to time. The dark viscous product which solidified on cooling, dissolved almost completely in boiling 2*N*-hydrochloric acid. The *hydrochloride*, which separated in bright yellow needles almost completely on cooling, was collected. (Found: Cl=10·7. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N$, HCl requires Cl=10·6 per cent.) The hydrochloride was decomposed with cold dilute ammonia and the *benzylidene* compound was crystallised from absolute alcohol which deposited colourless stout needles, m. p. 205°. (Found: N=4·8. $C_{20}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N=4·7 per cent.)

2-Methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydroquinolino-6 : 5- α -pyrone.

A solution of the quinolino-pyrone (2 g.) in 40 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) was gently boiled for 5 hours with granulated tin (6 g.); the solution was diluted to 200 c. c., filtered, and the dissolved tin removed as sulphide. The filtrate was concentrated on the water-bath to about 100 c. c., cooled, and neutralised with ammonia, when the *tetrahydro-derivative* slowly crystallised in small glistening plates of a golden yellow colour. Crystallised once from 50 per cent. alcohol, it melted sharply at 179° (yield 1·1·2 g.). (Found: N=6·4. $C_{11}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N=6·5 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallised from strong solutions in long colourless needles.

On treatment with nitric acid, the tetrahydro-compound developed a deep pink colour. A similar result was produced in an attempt to prepare the dichromate when the substance darkened and gradually decomposed.

The *picrate* and the *chloroplatinate* formed clusters of sharp pale yellow needles. (Found: Pt=23·00. $C_{13}H_{13}O_2N$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt=23·2 per cent.)

The *N-nitroso*-derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from alcohol in colourless prismatic needles, m. p. 160-161°. (Found: N = 11.0. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3N_2$ requires N = 11.4 per cent.).

The *acetyl* derivative separated from alcohol in colourless plates, m. p. 138-139°, and the *methiodide* from concentrated aqueous solutions in yellow plates, m. p. 202° (decomp.). (Found: I = 35.7. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2NI$ requires I = 35.6 per cent.).

2-Methyl-7:8-benzoquinolino-6:5- α -4'-methyl pyrone.

A mixture of 6-amino-4-methyl-1:2-naphthapyrone (2 g.), fuming hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.), and paraldehyde (6 g.) was saturated with hydrogen chloride and the product worked up as before. The product was yellow owing to the presence of some unchanged amino-naphthapyrone: it was therefore acetylated and the quinolino-pyrone extracted with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. Alkali precipitated from the extract a colourless solid which was insoluble in water, sparingly soluble in alcohol, and more readily soluble in chloroform or pyridine. It was best crystallised from chloroform which gave colourless prismatic needles, m. p. 248° (yield 0.6 gm.). (Found: C = 78.35; H = 4.75. $C_{18}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C = 78.5; H = 4.7 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* separated from a concentrated solution in small, colourless needles, and the *picrate*, from alcohol, in yellow prisms.

The *dichromate* formed dark yellow, short, prismatic needles. (Found: $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3=20.0$. $(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$, $\text{H}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ requires $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3=19.8$ per cent.)

The *chloroplatinate* crystallised in pale yellow, rhombic plates. (Found: $\text{Pt}=20.5$. $(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires $\text{Pt}=20.3$ per cent.)

The *mercurichloride* separated from concentrated solutions in lustrous triangular plates, and the *mercuriodide* formed pale yellow, prismatic needles.

*2-Methyl-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-7:8-benzoquinolino-
6:5-a-4'-methylpyrone*

This was prepared by reducing the naphthaquinolino-pyrone with tin and hydrochloric acid and working up the product as before. It crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m. p. 204° . (Found: $\text{C}=77.65$; $\text{H}=6.2$. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires $\text{C}=77.8$; $\text{H}=6.0$ per cent.)

The *chloroplatinate* formed pale yellow tapering needles. (Found: $\text{Pt}=20.1$. $(\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires $\text{Pt}=20.1$ per cent.)

The *N-nitroso-derivative* crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 168° (decomp.), and the *acetyl derivative* formed colourless plates, m. p. 202° .

2:4-Dimethyl-quinolino-6:5-a-pyrone.

A mixture of paraldehyde and acetone (1:1) was kept saturated with hydrogen chloride for 2 days. To

10 c.c. of it a mixture of 6-aminocoumarin (4 g.) and fuming hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.) was added and the whole was saturated with hydrogen chloride and left at the ordinary temperature for 24 hours. The reaction was then completed by heating at 130-140° for 4 hours and the dry mass was worked up as before. The product still contained a small quantity of the α -methyl derivative which was removed by washing twice with a little boiling alcohol in which the dimethyl compound dissolved rather sparingly. It was finally crystallised from hot pyridine and a little water, separating in colourless needles, m. p. 265°. The amount of the pure product obtained seldom exceeded 1.5 gm. (Found: C=74.5; H=5.4; N=6.0. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C=74.7; H=4.9; N=6.2 per cent.)

The *hydrochloride* formed colourless cubical crystals. (Found: Cl=13.75. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2N \cdot HCl$ requires Cl=13.6 per cent.).

The *dichromate* crystallised in deep yellow needles.

(Found: Cr_2O_3 =23.15. $(C_{14}H_{11}O_2N)_2 \cdot H_2Cr_2O_7$ requires Cr_2O_3 =22.75 per cent.)

The *chloroplatinate* formed yellow plates. (Found: Pt=22.7. $(C_{14}H_{11}O_2N)_2 \cdot H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt=22.7 per cent.)

The *picrate* crystallised from alcohol in short, stout, pale yellow needles. (Found: N=11.7. $C_{20}H_{14}O_9N_4$ requires N=12.3 per cent.)

The *mercurichloride* formed colourless prisms.

2 : 4-Dimethyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-quinolino-
6 : 5-a-pyrone.

After reduction with tin and hydrochloric acid for more than 12 hours, 2 g. of the dimethyl compound gave only 0.2 g. of the tetrahydro derivative crystallising from dilute alcohol in golden yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 121°. The unchanged material was mostly recovered being practically insoluble in dilute alcohol. (Found: N=6.3. $C_{14}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N=6.1 per cent.)

The N-nitroso derivative formed clusters of colourless needles melting at 177°, and the benzoyl derivative crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colourless, elongated plates, m. p. 171°.

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